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ABOUT THE MECHANISM OF MECHANOLUMINESCENCE OF GRAPHITE AND GRAPHENE

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Abstract

Mechanoluminescence covers the phenomena of luminescence arising from various types of mechanical effects (friction, impact, stretching, compression, etc.) on metals, crystals, polymers, etc. There are two main points of view on the occurrence of mechanoluminescence during the destruction of dielectrics: some authors attribute it to a gas discharge between the edges of growing cracks, while others attribute it to electron-excited free radicals on the edges of cracks. The purpose of this article is to propose a new mechanism for the occurrence of mechanoluminescence in solids using graphite and graphene as an example. We have shown that the energy of deformation under external influence is spent on heat, acoustic emission, field emission, and mechanoluminescence. It was found that the mechanoluminescence spectra of graphite contain a peak at 2.27 eV (547 nm) and for graphene – 2.0 eV (620 nm).

Keywords: graphite, graphene, surface layer, mechanoluminescence, crystal, energy, deformation, spectrum, emission.

Introduction

In recent years, the use of mechanoluminescent sensing elements in pulse (dynamic) pressure sensors for control systems of mobile and stationary mechatronic and robotic devices has become relevant. The term "mechanoluminescence" (ML) covers the phenomena of luminescence that occur during various types of mechanical effects (friction, impact, stretching, compression, etc.) on metals, crystals, polymers, etc. There are two main points of view on the occurrence of ML in the destruction of dielectrics: some authors [1] attribute it to a gas discharge between the edges of growing cracks, while others [2] attribute it to electronically excited free radicals on the edges of

cracks. Despite the rapidly increasing flow of works devoted to the study of ML, the nature of the emitting centers still causes heated discussion.

The aim of this article is to propose a new mechanism for the occurrence of mechanoluminescence in solids using graphite and graphene as an example.

Graphite and graphene

Until the mid-20th century, graphite was used as pencils, for electrodes, anodes, etc. Then it began to be used in metal production, in nuclear power engineering, in aviation and space technology [1-3]. The end of the 20th and the beginning of the 21st century were marked by the discovery of fullerenes (1985) [4], carbon nanotubes (1991) [5] and graphene (2004) [6]. The structure diagrams of graphite and graphene are shown in Fig. 1.

a)

b)

Figure 1. Graphite and graphene

Multilayer graphene or graphite is a layered 3D structure. Each layer consists of regular hexagons of carbon atoms (C) measuring 0.335 nm, between which strong covalent bonds act with an energy of 170 J/mol. Between the layers there is a space of 0.7-1.6 nm, where weak Van der Waals forces act with an energy of 16.7 J/mol (Fig. 1a). One layer of graphite is called graphene (Fig. 1b) [6]. There are reviews on the properties of graphene [7-9]. We will not touch on them.

We first determined the thickness of the surface layer of graphite and graphene in [10-13] (Fig. 2a). Fig. 2b shows the corrugations on the surface of graphene.

Figure 2. - Scheme of a solid: nanolayer → mesolayer → bulk phase (a); corrugated graphene (b).

In [12], it is shown that the surface energy of a bulk metal γ_2 is equal:

$$\gamma_2 = 0,7 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T_m \text{ [J/m}^2\text{]}, \quad (2)$$

where T_m is the melting temperature of the metal (K).

In the R(I) layer, the size effect must be taken into account and the surface energy becomes equal to γ_1 [13]:

$$\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 (1 - R(I)/R(I) + h) \approx 0,5\gamma_2, \quad (3)$$

where $\gamma_{12} = 0$ due to the second-order phase transition.

The thickness of the surface layer R(I) is given by the formula [10]:

$$R(I) = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot \alpha \cdot v \text{ [m]}. \quad (1)$$

In equation (1) you need to know one parameter – the molar volume of the element, which is equal to $v = M/\rho$ (M is the molar mass, ρ is its density), $\alpha = 1 \text{ mol m}^{-2}$ is a constant to maintain the dimensionality (R(I) [m]).

To separate the R(I) layer from the rest of the crystal, energy must be expended, which is called the specific adhesion energy:

$$W_a = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 - \gamma_{12} \approx \gamma_1 + \gamma_2. \quad (4)$$

We calculate the internal stresses σ_{is} between phases γ_1 and γ_2 :

$$\sigma_{is} = \sqrt{W_a \cdot \bar{L} / R(I)}, \quad (5)$$

where E is the Young's modulus of elasticity.

Using (1), we calculate the parameters of graphite and graphene (Table 1).

Table 1.

Surface layer thickness R(I) of graphite and graphene						
Carbon	M, g/mol	ρ , g/sm ³	R(I) _a , nm	R(I) _c , nm	γ_a , mJ/m ²	γ_c , mJ/m ²
Graphite	12,0107	2,26	0.900 (3)	2.46 (3)	2195	130
Graphene	12,0107	2,26	0,246 (1)	0,14 (1)	2652	-

It follows from Table 1 that the thickness of the surface layer of graphite is 0.9 and 2.46 nm, i.e. they represent a nanostructure. In graphite, the number of monolayers in the R(I) layer is three (3). Fig. 3a shows

how the internal pressure changes depending on the number of graphene layers [14]. Fig. 3b shows the intensity of the peak G of the Raman scattering of graphene depending on the number of its layers [15].

Figure 3. - Change in σ_{max} (red line) and P_{max} (green line) from the number of layers (a) [14]; line G from the number of layers (b) [15].

Both figures clearly show that the R(I) layer for graphite contains 3 graphene monolayers, which indicates the validity of our model (1). More than three layers of graphene turn into graphite and the values of the

quantities in Fig. 3 cease to depend on the number of layers. Using (2-5), we determine the elastic properties (Table 2).

Table 2.

Elastic parameters of graphite and graphene.

Carbon	W_{aa} , J/m ²	W_{ac} , J/m ²	σ_{isa} , GPa	σ_{isc} , GPa	E_{da} , eV	E_{dc} , eV
Graphite	2,853	1,690	4,9	1,36	2,27 (547 nm)	1,42
Graphene	5,304	-	118,4		2,00 (620 nm)	-

Here $E_d = W_a R(I) a$ (a is the lattice constant) is the “latent” energy of deformation. From Table 2 it follows that graphene has significant internal stresses σ_{isa} leading to its warping (Fig. 2b) [16].

Mechanoluminescence of graphite and graphene

According to the work [17], the energy of deformation under external influence is spent on heat, acoustic emission, field emission and mechanoluminescence. This means that the ML spectra of graphite and graphene will look as shown in Fig. 4 in accordance with Table 2.

Figure 4. – ML spectra of graphite (a) and graphene (b)

Let us compare the results obtained in Table 2 and Fig. 4 with the experimental values obtained in various works. Let us start with the work [18], where the IR

laser-induced radiation of carbon materials was experimentally investigated. Broadband radiation spectra in the visible region of the spectrum were discovered (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. - Emission spectra of carbon materials: massive polycrystalline graphite (1) and carbon black (2) in vacuum (a) and in air (b) [18]

From Figure 5, one can see a large coincidence of the spectra for graphite. We did not find any literature sources on graphene luminescence. From Table 2, Figure 4, one can see that the ML falls into an inconvenient

region on the edge of IR radiation (invisible light), while for graphite it falls into the green glow region. This is confirmed in the Raman spectra (Figure 6).

Figure 6. - 2D Raman band of graphite and graphene (a); number of graphite monolayers (b)

The first monolayer of graphite is graphene, it is determined by the unique physicochemical properties of graphene, such as a large theoretical specific surface area ($\sim 2600 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$), charge carrier mobility ($\sim 200,000 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$), high Young's modulus ($\sim 1000 \text{ GPa}$), thermal conductivity ($\sim 5000 \text{ W/m K}$), optical transparency ($\sim 97.7\%$), mechanical strength, etc. [19, 20].

Bilayer graphene differs from single-layer graphene and graphite. It is studied [21] due to the controlled width of the band gap. An analogue of bilayer graphene is SW graphene, which is more stable than graphene [22].

Three-layer graphene differs from the latter two in mobility and conductivity [23]. A special feature of three-layer graphene is that after it is twisted at a magic angle, it develops superconductivity, which can withstand magnetic fields 2-3 times greater than the Pauli limit for spin-singlet pairing [24].

In [25], photoluminescence images were obtained using femtosecond laser excitation on twisted bilayer graphene samples. The emission images were obtained by tuning the excitation laser energies in the near infrared range. The authors demonstrate an increase in photoluminescence emission at excitation energies that depend on the twist angle of the bilayer. The results show

a peak in light emission when the excitation is in resonance with transitions in van Hove singularities in the electron density of states. The authors measured the photoluminescence position for samples with different twist angles, showing resonances in the energy range from 1.2 eV (1033 nm) to 1.7 eV (729 nm). We have not found anything similar since this work. In [26], superlattices based on single-layer and bilayer graphene are considered. They are actively studied for use in optoelectronics, acoustics, nanoplasmonics, etc. The author of the work [26] showed that based on the analysis of the dispersion equations of a superlattice consisting of alternating strips of single-layer and two-layer graphene, the parameters of the energy spectrum of which can be regulated by changing the external electric field perpendicular to the surface of the sample, obtained using the Kronig-Penny model, it was shown that the energy spectrum of such a superlattice can be approximated by the Kane model. The absorption coefficient of light during interband transitions in such a structure was calculated.

Conclusion

Luminescence is directly related to the band diagram of a solid, reflects the relaxation features of electronic excitations – electrons, holes, excitons, created

in a solid by external irradiation, allows us to establish the energy scheme of local impurity centers and defects of the crystal structure. In addition, the phenomenon of luminescence has found wide application in science and technology, is a powerful tool for studying physical processes in condensed matter and is used in various areas of human activity.

The model of mechanoluminescence of graphite and graphene proposed by us opens the way to the application of the obtained results in optoelectronics of graphene and graphene-like structures.

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